

SERUM ANNEXIN A1 AS AN EARLY BIOMARKER OF STRUCTURAL PROGRESSION IN AXIAL SPONDYLOARTHRITIS

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ABSTRACT

Axial spondyloarthritis (AksSpA) is a chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease characterized by progressive structural damage of the spine, resulting in functional impairment and early disability. Early identification of structural progression remains challenging, particularly during non-radiographic stages. Annexin A1 (ANXA1) is an endogenous anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory protein involved in the regulation of inflammatory responses and tissue remodeling; however, its clinical significance in axSpA has not been sufficiently studied

Background

Axial spondyloarthritis (AksSpA) is a chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease characterized by progressive structural damage of the spine, resulting in functional impairment and early disability. Early identification of structural progression remains challenging, particularly during non-radiographic stages. Annexin A1 (ANXA1) is an endogenous anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory protein involved in the regulation of inflammatory responses and tissue remodeling; however, its clinical significance in axSpA has not been sufficiently studied.

Objective

To evaluate the clinical significance of serum annexin A1 levels in relation to disease activity and structural spinal progression in patients with axial spondyloarthritis.

Materials and Methods

A total of 62 patients with axSpA at different clinical and radiological stages (mean age 43.2 ± 5.3 years; mean disease duration 2.4 ± 1.4 years) were enrolled. Patients were classified into non-radiographic, established, and advanced stages of the disease. The control group consisted of 10 age- and sex-matched healthy individuals. Disease activity and functional status were assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), ASDAS, DAREA, and BASFI indices. Structural spinal damage was evaluated using the modified Stoke Ankylosing Spondylitis Spine Score (mSASSS/RASSS) and BASRI indices. Serum ANXA1 levels were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Statistical analysis was performed using standard methods.

Results

Serum ANXA1 levels were significantly lower in axSpA patients compared with healthy controls ($p < 0.05$). A gradual decline in ANXA1 concentration was observed with increasing disease duration and radiographic stage. Reduced ANXA1 levels were negatively correlated with disease activity indices (ASDAS, VAS) and positively associated with the severity of structural spinal damage (RASSS, BASRI). Importantly, decreased ANXA1 levels were detected already at the non-radiographic stage, indicating the presence of subclinical inflammatory and structural changes.

Conclusion

Serum annexin A1 represents a promising early biomarker of structural spinal progression in axial spondyloarthritis. Alterations in ANXA1 levels occur at early, non-radiographic stages and correlate with disease activity and structural damage, supporting its potential utility in early diagnosis and prognostic evaluation of axSpA.

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